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Determination of Zinc in Milk Samples using 1-(2-Quinolylazo)-2,4,5-trihydroxybenzene as Spectrophotometric Reagent

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ZINC is an essential metal in biological system and its essentiality for human being was recognised only recently. Zinc has been found considerably in milk samples and in this paper the trace amounts of the metal has been determined spectrophotometrically by 1-(2-quinolylazo)-2,4,5-trihydroxybenzene (QATB)¹. The method is simple and rapid.

Experimental

Synthesis of QATB: Stoichiometric amounts of 2-hydrazinoquinoline² (1.59 g, 0.01 mol, dissolved in the minimum amount of dilute hydrochloric acid) and 2,5-dihydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone³ (1.4 g, 0.01 mol in ethanol) were mixed and refluxed for 30 min. The solution was then cooled and made ammoniacal. Excess of ammonia was boiled off and the solution was allowed to stand overnight. The dark red precipitate obtained was recrystallised from ethanol and dried over phosphorus pentoxide. The purity of the compound was checked by thin layer chromatography and elemental analysis (Found: C, 64.2; H, 3.8; N, 15.1. C₁₅H₁₁N₂O₃ requires: C, 64.05; H, 3.91; N, 14.95%). A 1 × 10⁻³ M reagent solution was prepared. Reagent solutions were discarded when a week old.

Preparation of solutions: A 1 × 10⁻³ M stock solution of zinc was prepared by dissolving appro-

priate amount of analytical grade zinc(II) sulphate heptahydrate in water, standardised complexometrically with EDTA⁴, and further diluted as required for working standards. A fresh 1% solution was prepared and kept in amber-coloured bottle. A 0.5 N NaOH solution was prepared.

Standard calibration curve for zinc: To a suitable aliquot containing zinc (2.8-9.0 μg) were added 1% ascorbic acid (0.5 ml) and 1 × 10⁻³ M QATB (1 ml). A 0.5 N NaOH solution (2.0 ml) was then added and diluted to 10 ml keeping the final concentration of ethanol to 40% (v/v). The absorbance was measured at 560 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Addition of an ethanolic solution of QATB to a very dilute solution of zinc(II), in a medium containing not less than 30% (v/v) ethanol (otherwise a precipitate was obtained), resulted in a dark brown colour in alkaline solution having λ_{max} at 560 nm. The colour intensity was shown maximum and constant at 0.05-0.25 N NaOH, and 25 molar excess of reagent was required for complete complexation. Beer's law validity range with optimum concentration range in ppm is 0.0-1.37 and 0.28-0.9, respectively. Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity are 0.0012 μg Zn/cm² and 5.4 × 10⁴ dm² mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, respectively. The composition (M : L) determined by Job's method is 1 : 2. The method is highly sensitive as well as selective for zinc, and the transition metals either do not form complex with QATB in high alkaline medium or if formed by a few, are masked by cyanide except manganese. In absence of manganese(II), zinc ions which are also masked by cyanide, are demasked by adding formaldehyde solution, and this procedure was applied to find out trace levels of zinc in milk samples.

Effect of foreign ions: Effect of diverse ions on the colour development of zinc complex with QATB was studied by taking 0.65 μg ml⁻¹ of zinc(II), adding varying amounts of diverse ions and following the recommended procedure. It was observed that fluoride, nitrate, nitrite, sulphate, sulphite, alkaline earths, lanthanides, aluminium(III), indium(III), antimony(III), bismuth(III), chromium(III), platinum metals (except palladium) and thorium(IV) did not interfere at all. However, sulphide and manganese(II) interfered seriously. Cyanide also interfered but a 150-fold cyanide concentration is tolerated in presence of 1% formaldehyde solution. This is due to instability of tetracyanozincate ions in presence of formaldehyde⁵ and zinc ions are again free to interact with the reagent. Results of tolerance limits, in parts per million (given in parenthesis) of various ions in solution that caused a deviation smaller than ± 2% in absorbance are as follows: chloride (600), bromide (600), iodide (100), thiosulphate (100), phosphate (50), bromate (20), thiocyanate (40), citrate (40), tartarate (40), oxalate (20), EDTA (25), Fe²⁺ (56, masked by 1%

CN⁻), Ni²⁺ (25, masked by 1% CN⁻), Co²⁺ (25, masked by 1% CN⁻), Cu²⁺ (20, masked by 1% CN⁻), Pb²⁺ (10, masked by EDTA), Mo⁶⁺ (40), W⁶⁺ (40), U⁶⁺O₈ (20), V⁵⁺ (20, masked by 1% CN⁻), Cd²⁺ (20), Hg²⁺ (20) and Ag⁺ (10, masked by EDTA).

Determination of zinc in milk samples: Dry ashing method⁶ was used in determining the zinc contents of milk. Milk (25 ml) was added dropwise to a heated crucible to evaporate without forthing and after removal of moisture it was heated strongly to 450-500°. Concentrated nitric acid (1 ml) was added after cooling. It was then evaporated to dryness and ignited again at 450-500° for ~ 1h. Care was taken to avoid loss by sputtering. The resulting white ash was dissolved in the minimum amount of dilute nitric acid and made up to 25 ml in a standard flask. To the aliquot (1 or 2 ml), was added 0.1% KCN solution (0.5 ml) to mask the interfering metals and then 1% formaldehyde (1 ml) was added and zinc was determined by the recommended procedure.

Recovery of zinc from milk samples: The standard milk samples were spiked by adding known amounts of zinc and the total zinc was determined with the reagent. Table 1 reports the recovery data obtained with QATB and confirms the precision of the method. It was noted that zinc contents were variable in samples taken from different animal and breed, as well as time of the lactation process. Another factor of variation might be dependent upon the feed, age and health of the animal. It was also noticed that milk samples kept overnight in galvanised utensils have slightly higher zinc contents, which may be due to contamination of zinc during pasteurisation.

TABLE 1—RESULTS AND RECOVERY DATA FOR ZINC IN VARIOUS MILK SAMPLES WITH QATB AS REAGENT*

Milk samples	Zn ²⁺ found μg ml ⁻¹	Zn ²⁺ added μg ml ⁻¹	Zn ²⁺ recovered μg ml ⁻¹	Range of % recovery
Cow	3.67, 3.52, 3.81, 4.07	2.8	6.67, 6.12, 6.48, 6.80	96.83–103.09
Buffalo	2.98, 3.28, 3.06, 3.25	2.8	5.90, 6.05, 5.63, 5.83	96.08–102.99
Goat	3.84, 4.09, 3.57, 4.02	2.8	6.86, 7.02, 6.45, 6.72	98.97–103.31
Govt. supply (skimmed milk)	4.15, 3.90, 4.20, 4.08	2.8	6.70, 6.93, 6.80, 6.98	96.40–103.42

* Number of analyses = 4.

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Rapid Method for the Determination of Coking Value of some Carbonaceous Materials

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THE coking value is a measure of the amount of carbon (coke) left on heating a sample of carbonaceous materials, like tar, pitch and similar products, under specified conditions. The coking value is generally determined by Conradson carbon method¹. A simple, convenient and elegant method has been developed by the authors in this laboratory.

Experimental

The apparatus very similar to that used for proximate analysis of coal can be employed in the present method. The muffle furnace in addition to having rapid heat regaining capacity, should have an arrangement to exclude air circulation inside the furnace during the experiment. It is worth mentioning that heating may be done either by gas or electricity. A steady temperature of 570±5° should be maintained and sample heated for 7 min for the determination of coking value.

Accurately weighed sample (0.5-2.0 g) is taken in the silica crucible (specifications in Table 1). To

TABLE 1—SPECIFICATIONS OF THE SILICA CRUCIBLE* (DIMENSIONS IN MM)

Crucible	Lid
1. Height : 38	Internal dia. : 27
2. External dia. : 25	Dia. of well : 21
3. Internal dia. : 22	Depth of the well : 4
4. Combined weight of the crucible and lid should be between 12-14 gms.	
5. Maximum clearance between crucible and lid, at the top edge of the crucible should be 0.5 mm.	

*Crucible must be cylindrical, translucent, with a lid of capsule type.

this accurately weighed inert material (2-3 g), i.e. sand of specified grade², (Table 2), is mixed.